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INCREASING THE EVALUATION OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS BY INVESTING IN INNOVATIVE PRODUCTION PROCESSES

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ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ОЦЕНКИ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННЫХ ПРОЕКТОВ ПУТЁМ ИНВЕСТИРОВАНИЯ В ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПРОЦЕССЫ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА

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Abstract

The article discusses the issue of increasing the assessment of investment projects by investing in innovative production processes, as one of the important aspects of economic growth, and also examines the impact of innovation in development in companies.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается вопрос о повышении оценки инвестиционных проектов путём инвестирования в инновационные процессы производства, как один из важных аспектов экономического роста, а также рассмотрено влияние инновации в развитии в компаниях.

Keywords: innovation, growth, evaluation of investment projects, competitiveness, management technologies.

Ключевые слова: инновации, рост, оценка инвестиционных проектов, конкурентоспособность, технологии управления.

Introduction

The introduction of innovative processes into production is a necessary condition for economic growth and improving the quality of life in any country. It depends on the economic, scientific and technical potential of the state, its innovation policy and resources, and determines the level of competitiveness of the country. The globalization of scientific and innovation processes in the global market space requires the use of new organizational mechanisms to implement the transition to an innovative economy. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Innovation Activity" was developed in pursuance of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 8, 2017 No. UP-5185 and in order to implement the roadmap for the effective implementation of the Concept of administrative reform of the Republic of Uzbekistan to strengthen innovation activity¹, which shows that it is urgently important to study the theoretical and practical aspects of risk analysis in assessing the effectiveness of investment projects when introducing innovative processes into production.

Theoretical analysis of the research

Innovation ensures the sustainable functioning and development of any industry, since a characteristic feature of the modern economy is the high rate of change within industries and individual organizations, requiring the introduction of innovations. Under the influence of a changing external environment, enterprises change not only their product range, pricing policy and promotion methods, but also their organizational structure, standards and management technologies. The most effective way of change, development and implementation of innovations is determined using an innovation strategy based on long-term forecasting, taking into account internal and external factors and resource limitations. An innovation strategy involves creating a product that has no analogues on the market, focused on new needs. The theoretical and methodological foundation of innovative growth of the national economy begins with the theory of economic development of J. Schumpeter, in which he defined innovation as one of the factors of economic reproduction of an entrepreneur, determining the progress of the economic system. N.D. Kondratiev in the 20s. last century, he substantiated

¹ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Innovation Activity" dated September 8, 2017 No.5185.

ated the theory of large cycles of economic development lasting 50–60 years and proved that the transition to a new cycle is associated with technical progress - inventions and discoveries, changes in production and exchange techniques. In the second half of the twentieth century, the essence of innovation was interpreted by many scientists, such as F. Betts, T. Bryan, J. Grossi, etc.² The desire for greater economic freedom has led to a doubling in the size of the global economy in recent decades. This progress has lifted hundreds of millions of people out of poverty and reduced global poverty by two-thirds. Greater economic freedom has had a positive impact not only on the number of people living in poverty, but also on the degree of poverty that some still experience. For those still living in poverty, levels of individual-level deprivation in education, health and living standards are on average significantly lower in

countries with higher levels of economic freedom. Economic freedom has declined slightly over the past year. Around the world, internal tensions between the controlling tendencies of governments and the entrepreneurial freedom of free markets have increased, most notably in the rise of protectionism and politically motivated government spending.

Methodological analysis of the research

The research for evaluating investment projects examined the methods used by international financial institutions and foreign companies: The World Bank; European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD); Goldman, Sachs & Co.; Ernst & Young; United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) and Little-Mirrllis. In world practice, the method for evaluating the effectiveness of investment projects proposed by the World Bank Group.

Fig. 2. The main methods for assessing the effectiveness of investment projects[1]

In the statistical method for evaluating the effectiveness of investment projects, two indicators are calculated. Including:

1. Return on investment indicator - ROI[2]:

$$ROI = \frac{I-C}{C} * 100\% \quad (1)$$

where: I - revenue, C - expenses.

2. The return on investment (PP) is an important indicator that provides a simplified way to know how long it will take to recover the initial costs and is calculated using the following formula[3]:

$$PP = \frac{IC}{P+P_1} \quad (2)$$

where: P - average cash receipts; IC - initial investment; P₁ - is the period of time from the start of the project implementation to reaching the design capacity.

The traditional method of efficiency of investment projects is assessed in a dynamic way according to four indicators.

1. Net cash flow value (NPV) - determines the project's own economic efficiency and compares several investment objects with each other [4]:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{CF_t}{(1+r)^t} - IC \quad (3)$$

where: CF - discounted cash flow; t - year of calculation;

r is the discount rate; n - discount period.

2. The profitability index (PI) is the main method when deciding on the choice of an investment project, which focuses on the speed with which the initial investment made in the project will be reimbursed by subsequent cash flows[3]:

$$PI = \frac{NPV}{IC} \quad (4)$$

3. Indicator of the discounted payback period of the investment

(DPP) - eliminates the disadvantage of the static method of the payback period and takes into account the value of money over time[5]:

$$DPP = \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{CF_t}{(1+r)^t} > IC \quad (5)$$

4. Internal rate of return (IRR) - shows the loan rate at which there will be no investment loss, all cash inflows and outflows in the amount will be equal to zero. In this case, the investment will be recouped by future cash flows from the project[6]:

$$NPV = -IC + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{CF_t}{(1+IRR)^t} = 0 \quad (6)$$

However, in world practice, among the dynamic methods for evaluating the effectiveness of the above investment projects, in some cases, they began to use a modified internal rate of return (MIRR). The Modified Internal Rate of Return (MIRR) is the rate of return on investment adjusted for the reinvestment rate and is calculated using the following formula [7].

$$MIRR = \sqrt[n]{\frac{\sum_i^N CF_i^+ (1+WACC)^{N-i}}{\sum_i^N \frac{CF_i^-}{(1+r)^t}}} \quad (7)$$

Where: CF_i⁺ - income of the i-th period; CF_i⁻ - costs (investments) of the i-th period; WACC is the weighted average cost of capital; r is the discount rate; N is the duration of the project. According to the authors, the need to use this methodology when assessing

² Макушина А. Ю. Роль малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства в инновационном развитии Республики Узбекистан. "BIZNES - ЭКСПЕРТ", №3 (135) - 2019.

the effectiveness of investments in the innovative development of enterprises in Uzbekistan[8]. The research shows that each of the listed indicators separately makes it possible to evaluate an investment project to one degree or another, complementing the result, and therefore it is recommended to use all the listed indicators for a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of investment projects[9]. Each indicator is used based on the objectives of evaluating investment projects.

Analysis of the research

World practice shows that small businesses produce almost 60 percent of gross domestic product, a third of industrial products, 98 percent of agricultural products, and also provide half of investments. In many areas, small businesses account for 70 to 90 percent of exports. During 6 months of this year, the number of business entities increased by 60 thousand³. As you know, the Doing Business rating reflects the level of ease of running a small and medium-sized business. Currently, a total of 11 indicators are assessed: job creation, obtaining building permits, access to electricity, property registration, access to credit, protection of minority investors, payment of taxes, cross-border trade, compliance mechanisms, bankruptcy, and the market labor. ease of editing. Doing Business is one of the most popular ratings describing the investment climate of countries. And most importantly, this is the level of research activity, which is one of the main indicators of the country's scientific and technological development and is calculated as the total number of scientific materials published in edited scientific journals and publications included in the index of scientific sources⁴.

According to the authors, investments and innovations serve to increase the profitability of the enterprise and expand production, as well as reduce variable and fixed costs, and reduce the cost of finished products. It should be noted that factors such as modernization, diversification, differentiation, widespread use of corporate governance principles, employee motivation play an important role in increasing the efficiency of investment projects in the development of innovative activities of enterprises. At the same time, promising investment projects will remain relevant in adapting the enterprise to modern market mechanisms. It is also important to constantly improve the methods of evaluating investment projects that serve the innovative development of the enterprise, the optimal use of advanced foreign experience.

Conclusion

The research of this topic allowed us to put forward the following conclusions:

1. In the context of the development of innovative activities of enterprises, it is advisable to widely use statistical and dynamic methods to help make the right decisions in improving the efficiency of evaluating investment projects. As a result of the study, the factors influencing the evaluation of projects were identified, and they were systematized. The expediency

of using a modified internal rate of return has been substantiated, which accurately reflects the cost and profitability of the project.

2. To make an optimal investment decision, the project organizers must carry out a lot of analytical and financial work, including, in particular, all calculations for the implementation of the investment project, as well as assessing the effectiveness of investment projects based on the concept of the time value of money.

3. Determination of the main directions of investment decisions based on the development of an investment project/program associated with the coordination of a system of general monitoring and control over the implementation of project investments in accordance with the intended goal. Almost all types and methods of financial calculations and financial ones can be used for this purpose, control ones, which, in turn, are accompanied by corresponding expected forecasts.

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³ <https://mfa.uz/> - Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

⁴ <https://invest.gov.uz/> - Agency for attracting foreign investments under the Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan.